

KEY FACTORS INFLUENCING EMPLOYEE RETENTION IN AN AFGHAN
CONSTRUCTION COMPANY

By

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Declaration of Authorship

I hereby declare that:

- This thesis for the masters in business administration degree at the American university of Afghanistan (AUAF) is my original work. I have written it under the supervision of the thesis supervisor assigned to me by the business department.
- To the best of my knowledge, I have accurately cited all sources I have used for this thesis.
- I have acknowledged those parts of this thesis which are based on the collaborative work with third parties other than my supervisor.
- I have not submitted this thesis or substantial parts of it for a degree or any other qualification at another institution.

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Abstract

The research was undertaken to find out the key factors influencing employee retention in an Afghan construction company. An important component in this study was the (XYZ) construction company's employees, who participated in this study and provided their insights to this study's main question: What are the key factors that influence employee retention in (XYZ) construction company. The research data collection was done through semi-structured questionnaire administered in a face-to-face environment with the twelve employees of (XYZ) construction company. The study data was collected in three weeks' timeframe; the interview locations remained undisclosed due to security reasons. Mixed method was used in the research as the demographic section of the questionnaire was analyzed through quantitative method and the open-ended questions section was analyzed using the thematic content analysis. The finding reveals that the career development opportunities, good work environment, rewards and supervisor support will impact employee retention in (XYZ) construction company. The researcher suggests a host of recommendations, including providing career development opportunities, a good work environment, rewards and supervisor support to the employees justly.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

This first chapter of the research paper includes study overview, contextualization statement, purpose of the study, design, methods, and analysis, application to practice and overview of the document.

1.1 Study overview

This research was conducted to determine the key factors that influence employee retention in (XYZ) construction company which is operating in different provinces of Afghanistan. The findings indicated that career development opportunities, good work environment, rewards and supervisor support will greatly impact employee retention in (XYZ) construction company.

1.2 Contextualization statement

A 1988 study showed that eighty-six percent of Organizations struggled with attracting new employees and fifty-eight percent of those organizations expressed challenges regarding retaining current employees (Ramlall, S., 2004). Although this study is considerably dated, the information is still relevant today. (Fitz-Enz, J. 1997) stated that the average company loses approximately one million United States dollar with every ten managerial and professional employees who leave the organization. Combined with direct and indirect costs, the total cost of an exempt employee turnover is a minimum of one year's pay and benefits, or a maximum of two years' pay and benefits (Ramlall, S., 2004). This means losing any of critical employees will have a huge economic impact on an organization. In addition to the financial loss, they also suffer the loss of knowledge and experience the individual(s) may have, one of the most valued

employee assets. These costs could be avoided by retaining the professional employees within a company, government, NGO, private and corporate businesses.

Although there is almost no research available on the issue in Afghanistan, such situations prevail in Afghan companies suffering from losing their key employees. Perhaps lack of retaining professional employees is one of the many reasons that most Afghan companies couldn't operate overseas.

This study aims to find the key factors that influence employee's retention in (XYZ) construction company which will be helpful for the sustainability of the company. As a consequence of the same cultural values and economic situation in the country, this study will also help other national and international organizations, NGOs, private companies and businesses especially in construction industry that are currently operating or wanting to operate in the future in Afghanistan. This study will give an overview of what employees want from their employers in Afghanistan and what would satisfy them to remain in the company or organization they are working for.

1.3 Purpose of the study

The main objective of conducting this research is to add to the almost negligent body of knowledge in this field – with little or no study done to help, retain employees in Afghan construction companies and to give an overview of the importance of employee retention in governments, national and international organizations, NGOs, private entities, construction companies and businesses which are operating in Afghanistan.

1.4 Design, methods, and analysis

The data was collected through face-to-face interviews conducted with the employees of (XYZ) construction company. Twelve participants were interviewed face-to-face from the main office of the construction company. The interview locations remain undisclosed due to security reasons.

The researcher used mixed method (quantitative and qualitative). According to (Tashakkori, A., & Creswell, J. W., 2007), A mixed method study involves the collection or analysis of both quantitative and/or qualitative data in a single study in which the data are collected concurrently or sequentially, are given a priority, and involve the integration of the data at one or more stages in the process of research. The demographic section of the questionnaire was analyzed through quantitative method and the open-ended questions section was analyzed using the thematic content analysis.

1.4.1 Research question

The main research question is: What are the key factors influencing employee retention in (XYZ) construction company.

Demographic data were analyzed using quantitative method and open-ended questions were analyzed using thematic content analysis.

1.5 Application to practice

This research could be used for policy makers and human resources professionals in the government or private sector especially construction companies operating in Afghanistan in creating employee retention strategies for their organizations.

1.6 Document overview

This research consists of five chapters. Chapter one offers an overview of all parts of this paper; chapter two explains the concepts and previous research related to the topic of this study; chapter three shows the method of data collection, why the method was selected, how data was collected and what challenges existed in data collection; chapter four shows the collected data and main findings and the analysis of the research; chapter five contains the conclusions and recommendations of the study. It further shows the limitations of the study and recommendations for future study.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Introduction:

In this chapter the author will discuss the importance of employee retention, employee retention definition, and the factors of employee retention (rewards, career development opportunities, supervisor support, work environment). Construction is a competitive sector in which the employees faces new challenges every day and also the employees have the pressure to compete with the co-workers to get a better position. As construction is a wide field, there could be numerous issues within the industry that could be discussed but the author chose this topic because the construction industry is facing massive challenges in retaining key employees and maintaining the employee turnover.

2.2 Importance of employee retention:

A study on Determinants of Employee Retention in telecom sector of Pakistan telecom sector of Pakistan by (Shoaib M., Noor A., Tirmizi S.R, Bashir S., 2009) with 130 responses from 150 respondents regarding the impact of career development opportunities, supervision support, working environment, rewards and work life policies on employee retention, reveals the positive relationship between career development opportunities, supervision support, working environment, rewards and work life policies with employee retention.

A study on Relationship between Employee Turnover and Employee Compensation in small business by (Hope, J. B., & Mackin, P. C. (2007) explores the relationship between employee turnover and firm size as it relates to compensation using the National longitudinal survey of youth (NLSY). The purpose of the study was to examine whether employee turnover differences between small and large firms are the result of differences in wages and benefits or of

some form of self-selection where employees of small businesses are simply more prone to high turnover rates than those in larger firms. According to observations by Hope and Mackins (2007), employees of large establishments stay in their jobs longer than employees of small establishments. Offering benefits improve employee retention. When a firm offers benefits, it decreases the probability of an employee's leaving in a given year by 26.2 percent and increases the probability of staying an additional year by 13.9 percent. The earnings results based on the relationship between establishment size and earnings show that firm size positively impacts earnings for service and manufacturing occupations.

A study on strategies for improving employee Retention by Cordery J. (2006) has arisen as a consequence of growing concern within the meat processing industry regarding employee retention and turnover. This report stated that the increasing difficulties in retaining skilled, effective workers amounted to a looming crisis within the industry, and called for developing effective workforce retention strategies within the industry.

Stable predictors of job satisfaction, psychological strain, and employee retention: An evaluation of organizational change within the New Zealand Customs Service by Mansell, A., Brough, P., & Cole, K. (2006) wrote that changes in employment conditions have resulted in the increased exposure of workers to unfavorable job characteristics and consequential increases in adverse individual and organizational health outcomes. Staff retention and employee satisfaction significantly improved over time, and these increases were attributable to workplace improvements. Stable predictors of job satisfaction included minor daily stressors, positive work experiences, job control, and perceived supervisor support.

The study of The Interactive effects of Organizational Politics and Exchange Ideology on Manager Ratings of Retention by Andrews, M. C., Witt, L. A., & Kacmar, K. M. (2003),

examined the moderating effect of exchange ideology on the relationship between perceptions of organizational politics and manager-rated retention. Data collected from 178 employees of a distribution services organization indicated that employees' perceptions of organizational politics related negatively related to manager assessments of retention. However, the variables were only related to employees with a moderate to solid exchange ideology. These individuals were more sensitive to a political environment than individuals with a weak exchange ideology.

All that Glitters is not Gold: Employee Retention in Offshored Indian Information Technology Enabled Services by Thite M., (2010) Increasing offshoring of customer contact services to destinations such as India is underpinned by the availability of low cost and high-quality workforce. However, this competitive advantage is under threat with talent shortages, wage increases, and, most importantly, high employee attrition. Based on empirical studies and person-organization fit literature, the key issues and challenges in retaining talent in the Indian business are pay satisfaction, work organization, employment branding, and longer-term career advancement opportunities. It recognizes the need for multi-pronged retention strategies in a highly competitive, changing, and fast-growing part of the global services sector.

Employee engagement: conceptual issues by little B., (2008) the extant research on employee engagement demonstrates its relationship to outcome variables important to every organization, such as productivity, safety, employee retention, and customer service. If engagement is being used as a group level phenomenon, good research methods require that it be subjected to within-group and between-group variance tests.

Career planning key to employee retention by John N., (2000) with evolving technology fueling job and wage growth, the multifamily industry is forced to compete for top talent in new and nontraditional ways. Career Planning process developed a new approach to retain and

develop talent. Through an associate review that looks forward rather than backward, career planning helps the associate understand all the opportunities available within the firm.

Family-Responsive Variables and Retention-Relevant Outcomes among Employed Parents by Aryee S., Luk V., Stone R., (1998), This study examined the influence of family-responsive variables and the moderating influence of gender on the retention-relevant outcomes of organizational commitment and turnover intentions. Results of regression analysis revealed that satisfaction with work schedule flexibility and supervisor, work-family support were related to both retention-relevant outcomes. Contrary to our prediction, gender did not moderate the influence of any of the family-responsive variables on the retention-relevant outcomes.

2.3 Employee Retention:

(Frank, F. D., Finnegan, R. P., & Taylor, C. R., 2004, p. 13) defined employee retention as “the effort by an employer to keep desirable workers in order to meet business objectives”. Retention is the ability to hold onto those employees a firm wants to keep, for longer than competitors (Johnson, M., 2000). The retention should be analyzed at more than just a single level; the influence of employee retention can arise at multiple levels (Klein et al., 1994; Klein and Kozlowski, 2000; Raudenbush and Bryk, 2002; Yammarino and Dansereau, 2004 cited by Shoaib, M., Noor, A., Tirmizi, S. R., & Bashir, S., 2009). Retention is considered as a multifaceted component of an organization’s human resource policies. It begins with hiring the right people and persists with working agendas to keep them involved and devoted to the organization (Freyermuth, 2004 cited by Shoaib, M., Noor, A., Tirmizi, S. R., & Bashir, S., 2009).

2.4 Factors of Employee Retention:

This section is dedicated to explain and highlight various factors responsible for employee retention:

2.4.1 Rewards:

In several studies the word reward is somewhat that organizations offer to the employees in response to their performance and effective contributions and at the same time the desires of employees (Agarwal, 1998 cited in Sheikh and Qamar and Iqbal). Rewards are generally divided in two categories, extrinsic and intrinsic: Extrinsic rewards are tangible, like cash rewards such as bonuses, free trips, health insurance, car fuel etc., while Intrinsic rewards are intangible rewards such as naming a worker, employee of the month, word of praise etc. Organizations give rewards to employees in response to their contribution, so that the employees become motivated for future positive behavior. Rewards exert a long-lasting thought on the workers and demonstrates the worker's opinion that they are appreciated (Silbert, L.T., 2005 cited by Shoaib, M., Noor, A., Tirmizi, S. R., & Bashir, S., 2009). Rewards play a significant role in job satisfaction as they accomplish the basic necessities as well as facilitate achieving higher levels of goals. Earning is considered by the employees as the means to identify that either they are achieving by devoting their precious time, efforts and skills in a job (Bokemeier, J. L., & Lacy, W. B., 1987).

The reward system of any organization affects the employee performance and their aspiration to stay employed (Bamberger & Meshoulam, 2000, MacDuffie, 1995). Striking compensation offers accomplish the financial and substantial desires and is also considered as a means of establishing social networks by employee's ranks and place of authority in organization so it is the significant factor of retention. It is further described that a major difference among

workers exists in acknowledging the worth of financial rewards for employee retention (Pfeffer, J., 1998). As a consequence of performance and contribution, organizational rewards are the returns or benefits given to the employees as an appreciation and are regarded as the effective source of attracting and retaining (Lawler, 1981; Milkovich & Wigdor, 1991; Zenger, 1992). Knowledge workers play a significant role in the organization's long-term performance; therefore, they are employed by using striking types of compensation packages, and it is considered as substitution of loyalty among knowledge workers (Igarria, Greenhaus, & Parasuraman, 1991; Lum, Kervin, Clark, Reid & Sirola, 1998; Liu, 2004 cited by Foong-Ming, 2008). Retention is largely influenced by organizational rewards as it will have a satisfaction-impact on employees, also the employee's decision whether to stay or leave the organizations is highly focused on the competitive rewards given to them by the organization. Organizations attach the employees measurably and psychologically through these rewards (Becker, 1960), and considering these rewards as an acceptable form of appreciation, employees will stop thinking about opportunities from other organizations (Foong-Ming, 2008). Often effective compensation strategies offer organizations a competitive edge by enhancing their ability to attract and retain employees. Hence, the scope and administrative intricacy of compensation systems persist to enhance and the employees are getting more concerned in benefit cost restraint (cf. Bergmann, Bergmann, & Grahn, 1994 cited in Sinclair, Leo and Wright, 2005). Compensation and benefits are the most recognized and major factors among organizations' retention strategies. The influence of employee compensation, rewards and appraisals is described in most researches on turnover and retention (Becker and Huselid, 1999; Huselid, 1995; Milman, 2003; Milman and Ricci, 2004; Walsh and Taylor, 2007). Tremendously competitive wage systems endorse employee commitment and consequently attract and retain superior workforce (Becker and

Huselid, 1999; Shaw et al., 1998 cited in Moncarz, Zhao and Kay, 2009). Shaw et al.'s (1998) research further illustrated that employees will stay with an organization as long as it serves up their self-interest to do so better than the choices available to them elsewhere. (Moncarz, Zhao, Kay, 2009).

2.4.2 Career Development Opportunities:

Identifying developmental strategies that can motivate employee commitment to the mission and values of organizations in order to motivate them and assist the organization to achieve and maintain a competitive edge, is an emerging issue for the HR managers (Graddick, M.N., 1988, cited in Shoaib, M., Noor, A., Tirmizi, S. R., & Bashir, S., 2009). Gaining innovative skills and getting benefit of many diverse systems of learning beneficial to employees and organizations is what studies demonstrated as “Development” (Simonsen, 1997). Employees consider their capabilities on the job and think themselves responsible for their career whereas organizations benefit from encompassing skilled and more productive employees. Employees perceive skill development opportunities and career progress as major attractors to organizations (Kreisman, 2002; Dibble, 1999 cited in Kreisman, 2002). Hall, (2004) highlighted that Career development opportunities are considered imperative factors both in an organizational and individual context. Other studies stated it as a mutually beneficial process as it provides significant results to both parties, employees and the organization (Hall, 1996; Kyriakidou and Ozbilgin, 2004). To sustain a competitive edge, organizations need talented employees, and contrarily employees need career developing opportunities and competence development (Prince, B.J., 2005, cited by Shoaib, M., Noor, A., Tirmizi, S. R., & Bashir, S., 2009). Career development opportunities are imperative for both the organization and individual (Hall, 2004). It's a mutual benefit process because career development provides the important outcomes for

both parties (Hall, 1996; Kyriakidou and Ozbilgin, 2004). Organizations need talented employees for maintaining a sustainable competitive advantage and individuals to require career opportunities to develop and grow their competencies (Prince, 2005 cited in Madiha et al., 2009). Huselid (1995) argued that knowledge, skills and the abilities an organization's existing and prospective employees can be enhanced by holding on the career-related functions, and also improves the retention of quality workforce. Within the organizations, the opinion about prospects development opportunities motivates the employees for up to expectations performance, hence remain with the company to reveal their skills and abilities (Vroom, V. H. (1964) Promotion brings a positive change in employees, it signifies that organization is aware of and evaluating the employee's performance through formal promotion (Foong-Ming, 2008). To remain in the current jobs, career growth, learning, and development are the major three bases. A cooperative supervisor gives opportunities to learn, challenge, and grow in their jobs equivalent to their abilities and ambitions. A supervisor supports employees to develop the task itself along with their capabilities and keep themselves upgraded in their expertise (Kaye, B., & Jordan-Evans, S., 2003). Kanter (1977) determined that strongly controlled developmental opportunities cause employees to separate themselves from their bosses and strongly opposed organizational demands, particularly in larger organizations. Stout, L. A. (1988) stated, Employees presented negative responses to decreased promotional motivations and reduced organizational commitment, and even more inclination to quit the job. Hence negative responses from employees, including declined organizational commitment and increased chances to leave, are strongly influenced by enlarged job tenure (Taylor, Audia and Gupta, 1996). In a study of (Judge, T. A., Cable, D. M., Boudreau, J. W., & Bretz Jr, R. D., 1995), its stated that Employee's satisfaction with their career achievements is generally termed as career satisfaction also

evaluated as career success. Career satisfaction can be predicted through factors as goal-specific environmental maintenance and resources that offers social and material supports for the personal goals of employees (Barnett, B. R., & Bradley, L. (2007). From the aforementioned studies it can be argued that employees have a less propensity to leave only if they are learning and developing. Conversely, the employees instigate to externally seek for the better alternative job opportunity.

2.4.3 Supervisor Support:

Flynn, A. (2016) stated, ‘People don’t leave jobs, they leave managers’ it means that supervisor support is so essential to retain employees as employees may leave managers, not jobs. Association between workers and the boss is a significant factor that influences employee retention as supervisors are the “human face” of the organizations. Employee’s relationship with a supervisor strongly affects the employee’s opinion about the organization (Eisenberger, R., & Shanock, L., 2003). Supervisor’s support is an essential factor to change the worker’s propensity to quit and create high involvement in a job by establishing a strong relationship and free interaction with the supervisor (Greenhaus, J. H., Bedeian, A. G., & Mossholder, K. W., 1987). After a two-year survey of more than three thousand employees in different job functions and industries by (Kaye, B., & Jordan-Evans, S., 2003) demonstrated that managers, bosses, and team leaders or who direct and work together with workers have a significant influence on the satisfaction or dissatisfaction of employees with their jobs. Alternatively, it can be said that employees look for other opportunities elsewhere as a consequence of “problems with the boss”. Issues that exert or force employee satisfaction or commitment are mostly under the charge of manager, supervisor, or team leader. Supervisors play a significant and differentiated part distinguished from anyone else in the organization, so the supervisor becomes an essential

player. His role is as a catalyst i.e., one who understands each employee and reveals their distinctive ability, and adapt them into performance (Buckingham and Coffman, 1999 cited by Little, B., & Little, P., 2006). Managers must interact with every employee at a time to motivate and retain efficient workers. As satisfaction is considered the major element in employee's decision to quit or to stay in the organization, therefore a good boss will assist the efficient employees to seek satisfaction in their job (Buckingham, Coffman, 1999; Kreisman, 2002 cited by Kaye, B., & Jordan-Evans, S. (2000). Borstorff, P. C., & Marker, M. B., (2007) determined that workers desire trustworthy bosses who recognize them, appreciate them and behave fairly with them. Abusive supervisors incorporate conflicts in employee's attitudes regarding the job, life, and organization. According to Silbert, L., (2005) it is of no matter whether the environment is formal or informal, in larger organizations, employees react more to appraisals, encouragement, and supervisor support. She reported that well skilled and having good positions may seek similar job anywhere else, but the more effective mean to retention is to encourage support and widen close relationships on the job. Freyermuth (2007) illustrated that to properly establish the place where workers desire to stay, organizations need to groom up supervisors or managers. (cited by Irshad, M., & Afridi, F., 2007). The employee's capabilities can be improved by providing performance and opportunities at every level of their job (Otis, N., Grouzet, F. M., & Pelletier, L. G. (2005).

2.4.4 Work Environment:

Although learning and growing opportunities seem to be significant for employee retention (Arnold, R., 2005; Hytter, 2007; Michaels, E., Handfield-Jones, H., & Axelrod, B., 2001), an organization needs to develop a supportive learning and challenging work environment. Prior studies derived the idea of "learning and working environment" (Abrams, D.,

Rutland, A., Ferrell, J. M., & Pelletier, J., 2008; Birt, M., Wallis, T., & Winternitz, G., 2004). It generally relates with the climate where employees can learn and perform. Particularly, support and aspiration at work, the stress of work, degree of empowerment and the responsibility that workers acknowledge, alternatives in the job tasks and development, stipulation of challenging and significantly meaningful work and developmental opportunities, are the other concepts that describes the term working environment (Natalie et al., 2011, cited by Fatima, H., 2011). Major and significant factors in the job satisfaction of employees include challenging and meaningful work that distinguishes or generates contributions in society. These may be associated with one more significant factor: the desire for a sense of belonging to the group or team and in this way, they also want to feel linked to one's task and mainly to society through one's task. Being capable of controlling implying developments in work assignments, procedures, programs and measurements are included in this meaningful work climate. Employees get stressed with those bosses who control excessively with attention or did not delegate properly. Some employees feel satisfied by taking other's works responsibility on themselves and even more pleased in getting and achieving those challenges in the job. It makes the employees feel more pride in their achievements and is more excited in their work (Kaye, B., & Jordan-Evans, S., 2003). Miller, N. G., Erickson, A., & Yust, B. L., 2001), stated, workers think them to be valued in the work climate that offers them a sense of belonging. Various studies determined that employees with positive experience related to job hours, sense of job fulfillment, and a greater degree of job satisfaction have a lower propensity to leave their current bosses. Whether workers stay with the organization mainly depends on the level to which their workers or employees react to their expertise growth, although it is necessary to earn more salary and compensation enclosed with the job. They analyzed that most committed employees to accomplish challenging tasks are more

likely to stay with their companies (Walsh and Taylor, 2007 cited by Moncarz, E., Zhao, J., & Kay, C., 2009).

It is widely thought that work climate gives employees the opportunity to progress and develop, which is a critical factor to retention (Jamrog, J., 2004). A study by (Frank, F. D., Finnegan, R. P., & Taylor, C. R., 2004), stated that employee engagement and employee retention are joined at the hip. Declined propensity to leave and enhanced retention result from employee increased involvement (Council, C. L., 2004). Various practices e.g., rewards as a way of superior employee's retention, accepting everything considered valued in the employment relationship encourages employee involvement and engagement (Rumpel, S., & Medcof, J. W., 2006 cited in Nelson, K., & McCann, J. E., 2010).

Chapter 3: Methodology and Research Design

This research was conducted to find out the key factors that influence employee retention in (XYZ) Construction Company which is operating in different provinces of Afghanistan.

This is an exploratory and qualitative research. The research data collection was done through semi-structured questionnaire & face to face interviews conducted with the twelve employees of (XYZ) construction company. The study data was collected in three weeks' timeframe, the interviews' locations remained undisclosed due to security reasons.

The researcher used mixed method (quantitative and qualitative). The demographic section of the questionnaire was analyzed through quantitative method and the open-ended questions section was analyzed using the thematic content analysis. For the objective of the research, this approach is believed appropriate as a procedure of eliciting data required to draw an effective conclusion from the research study.

Within this study, the research framework is developed based on measuring the employees' job satisfaction at (XYZ) in relation to retention.

3.1 Methodological Fit

The researcher used mixed-method (quantitative and qualitative). According to (Tashakkori, A., & Creswell, J. W., 2007), a mixed methods study involves the collection or analysis of both quantitative and qualitative data in a single study in which the data are collected concurrently or sequentially, are given a priority and involve the integration of the data at one or more stages in the process of research. According to Runeson and Höst, the mixed-method has the capability to take into consideration both confirmatory and exploratory research questions within the same study. It has robust inferences than a single method. The integration of

qualitative and quantitative data always offers a better understanding of the studied concepts (Runeson, P., & Höst, M., 2009). Mixed methods have been described as the "third methodological movement" (following quantitatively and qualitatively oriented approaches) (Tashakkori, A., & Teddlie, C., 2003). Mixed method research is the systematic combination of qualitative and quantitative methods in research or evaluation. Greene (2007:13) provides the following definition of what she calls a mixed methods social inquiry: "(it) involves a plurality of philosophical paradigms, theoretical assumptions, methodological traditions, data gathering and analysis techniques and personalized understandings and value commitments. In this way different kinds of data are generated" (Schwandt. 2007:196 cited by Du Plessis, P., & Majam, T., 2010).

A mixed-methods design incorporates techniques from qualitative and quantitative methods to answer research questions (Byrne, 2006 cited by in Du Plessis, P., & Majam, T., 2010). Mixed methods social inquirers choose from a full repertoire of methodological options at any number of multiple points in an inquiry process – purpose, overall design, methods, sampling, data recording, analysis, and interpretation (Teddlie and Tashakkori, 2003:11 cited by Du Plessis, P., & Majam, T., 2010)

One to one, face-to-face and semi-structured questionnaires were the primary data collection method in this study.

To achieve the purpose of this study, the researcher used face-to-face interviews.

(Cachia, M., & Millward, L., 2011 cited by Donaldson, W. M., 2020) stated that face-to-face interviews are "long established as the leading means of conducting qualitative research" (Cachia, M., & Millward, L., 2011. p. 265). Casey, M. A. (2009) specified that interviews "can

provide insight into complicated topics when opinions or attitudes are conditional or when the area of concern relates to a multifaceted behavior or motivation” (p. 19).

Advantages of face to face interview, using qualitative methods include:

- Can involve reality (Alshenqeeti, H., 2014)
- Controlled answering order (Alshenqeeti, H., 2014)
- Relatively flexible (Alshenqeeti, H., 2014)
- participant involvement on the intellectual and emotional levels (Fontana, A., & Frey, J. H., 2005; O'Neill, K. K., 2011)
- plasticity in questioning (O'Neill, K. K., 2011)
- In-depth information about participants' inner values and beliefs (Ho, D. G. (2006)
- Discreetness that supports psychological safety for participants (O'Neill, K. K., 2011)
- Researcher access to communication rich elements that provide social cues such as body language, hand gestures and voice tone (Gable, G. G., 1994; Opdenakker, R., 2006; Conrad, C., & Poole, M. S., 2012)

(Casey, M. A., 2009) stated, “[t]he open-ended approach allows the subject ample opportunity to comment, to explain and to share experiences and attitudes” (p. 3) and it let “individuals to respond without setting boundaries or providing them clues for potential response categories” (p. 3). As such, interviews “contribute to the emergence of a more complete picture of the participants’ working environment and their everyday practices” (Schnurr, S., 2009, p.18).

Disadvantages of the face to face interviews, using qualitative method include:

- Time-consuming (Alshenqeeti, H., 2014)

- Small scale study (Alshenqeeti, H., 2014)
- Limiting relevant information from emerging due to over-structuring of the interview (Charmaz, K., 1994 cited by Holton, J. A., 2018)
- Never 100% anonymous (Alshenqeeti, H., 2014)
- Potential for subconscious bias (Alshenqeeti, H, 2014)
- Potential inconsistencies (Alshenqeeti, H, 2014)

The purpose of quantitative studies is for the researcher to project his or her findings onto the larger population through an objective process. Data collected, often through surveys administered to a sample or subset of the entire population, allow the researcher to generalize or make inferences. Results are interpreted to determine the probability that the conclusions found among the sample can be replicated within the larger population. Conclusions are derived from data collected and measures of statistical analysis (Creswell, 2002; Thorne and Giesen, 2002 cited by Borrego, M., Douglas, E. P., & Amelink, C. T., 2009).

3.2 Participants

All the participants were current employees of the head office of (XYZ) construction company located in Kabul, and the screens for the participants were as follow:

1. Ability to participate in English
2. Afghan
3. At least high school graduate
4. Above eighteen years of age and below sixty years
5. At least worked more than one year
6. Having full-time employment status

7. Willingness to participate in one face-to-face interview
8. Willingness to have their contributions to the study publicly disseminated
9. Identification as an engaged employee, Because I had an existing professional relationship with the participants, I was able to identify engaged employees.

The participant group consisted of twelve afghans that are employed at (XYZ) construction company in Kabul, Afghanistan: Three females and nine males; five aged between twenty to thirty, four aged between thirty-one to forty and three aged between forty-one to fifty; four participants are employed at managerial level, and the rest eight are employed in the officer level.

All participants were requested to sign an informed consent form at the start of the interview (Appendix A), approved/provided by the American University of Afghanistan for ethical purposes/clearance. The informed consent form asserted that the thesis research topic (What are the key factors influencing employee retention in a construction company). The researcher also informed the participants that their participation is voluntary, and this is not mandatory if they are not willing to participate. The participants can withdraw from the interview at any stage without any circumstances. Fortunately, all the research participants agreed and signed the consent forms and fully participated in the interview.

3.3 Sampling

The research sample was fair (N=12); according to (Reinecke, J., Arnold, D. G., & Palazzo, G., 2016) there is no single, objective answer as to how many interviews or hours of observation are sufficient. Few in-depth interviews with key respondents may provide focused insights into a particular niche area of research. However, broad claims about, for instance, field-

level changes may necessitate stronger evidence from more respondents representing multiple perspectives. While researchers may have the cooperation of an organization which allows for sufficient data to be gathered in a short period of time, impactful fields research can often require years of data gathering prior to analysis (Vaccaro, A., & Palazzo, G., 2015).

The sampling method was non-random, convenience sampling. Convenience sampling is the intentional choice of an informant because of their qualities, which allows the researcher to source people who are knowledgeable and willing to provide information (Tongco, M. D. C., 2007). Due to the size and nature of the organization and socio-cultural factors that inhibit participation in research and the specificity of the screens, convenience sampling was the most appropriate option. Employees with whom the researcher had an existing relationship (that encouraged openness, honesty, and disclosure) and who were identified as engaged were targeted for selection.

The study adopted a qualitative approach to assist in an understanding the experiences of the participants, all of whom had been identified as high-potential employees in the company; it sought to promote the understanding of a social problem through the rich description (Creswell, J. W., 2014)

3.4 Research Site

The (XYZ) construction company currently employs approximately sixty employees. It is a private sector organization. It is located in four-floor building in Kabul, Afghanistan. As Robert Merton mentioned, “[P]eople revealed sensitive information when they felt they were in a safe, comfortable place with people like themselves” (as cited in Casey, M. A., 2009, p. 3) The physical location of an interview is a critical element that needs to be addressed and to maintain

confidentiality, the interviews were done in a private but familiar meeting room within the office. As the findings of the study directly relate to the success of the organization and fell under the scope of the researcher's duties at the organization, permission was given to interview the participants during working hours.

3.5 Research Design

A case study design in a single organization was used to explore how participants construct meaning within their live contexts (Yin, R. K., 2009). In this way, an attempt was made to learn more about an unknown or inadequately understood subject by means of gathering in depth data (Leedy & Ormrod, 2001 as cited by Williams, C., 2007).

3.6 Questions

The questionnaire which was used in the interviews (Appendix B) had two main sections, section A was demographic questions, and section B was focused on the following open-ended questions:

1. What are three main reasons to work in the construction industry?
2. How are you motivated in your present job?
3. If you leave the job what will be one key factor prompting you to do so?
4. What kind of intrinsic or extrinsic rewards have you received in your current job and how frequently?
5. What do you expect from your employer?

To generate rich data, participants were asked the above questions that explored the key factors which will influence their retention in the (XYZ) construction company. At the beginning of the interview, broad and general questions were discussed but as the interview progressed, the

main questions, which were written in the questionnaire, approved by instructor/supervisor of the research, were discussed and the inputs of the interviewee were taken. Each interview began with greetings and informal chat, the researcher gave an open opportunity to the participants to ask their questions regarding the research details, most of them asked why the researcher is doing the research and where will be this research submitted, which were patiently answered by researcher and all the doubts the interviewee may have were cleared. The closing questions of the interview were: 'Is there anything you would like to share, or do you have any recommendations/suggestions, please?'. This question was ensuring that all relevant information was presented and not any necessary information was remained.

3.7 Answers

In line with the company's cultural values and to protect the privacy and anonymity of the participants, the findings were associated with the group rather than identifiable to the particular participant, and the names of the participants were replaced with a code which has no relation to the participants' names. Furthermore, to protect the participants' identity some of the data and analysis were not included in the study.

3.8 Instrumentation

Field notes were used as a method of data collection. Audio or video recording were not used in the interviews as the researcher knew, it was not acceptable due to social and company cultural values and privacy preferences of the respondents.

In addition to the company's cultural values, field notes have advantages like their cost, cost, reliability, and simplicity: no expensive equipment to purchase and set up (O'Neill, K. K. (2011).

According to Creswell, using qualitative and quantitative approaches together provides a better understanding of research problems than either direction alone (Creswell et al., 2003, cited by Mackenzie, N., & Knipe, S., 2006). Therefore, the researcher has used mixed research method, including quantitative method for the demographic questions and qualitative method for open ended questions.

3.9 Coding and analysis

The purpose of this study was to explore what are the key factors that influence employee retention in (XYZ) construction company. The inputs of the respondents were analyzed to answer to the main research question and the purpose of this study. As (Casey, M. A., 2009) stated that during analysis, not all questions or answers are of the same value because different questions have different purposes. The amount of time and attention to each question should be given according to its necessity and the main purpose of the research. Questions, such as opening questions, do not need to be analyzed (Casey, M. A., 2009). In this study, only four questions were analyzed. The goal of the other questions was to relax the respondents, to allow them to ‘warm up’ and to inspire their thoughts about the key factors that influence employee retention in construction company.

According to (Gillham, B., 2000, p.59) “Content analysis is about organizing the substantive content of the interview...there are two essential strands to the analysis: identifying those key, substantive points; putting them into categories”. To undertake the analysis of the participants discussions and content, the researcher applied the “Key Concepts” framework (Casey, M. A., 2009, p. 125). The main objective of the framework was to “to identify a limited number of important ideas, experiences, preferences that illuminate the study” (Casey, M. A., 2009, p. 125)

The researcher initially analyzed the data by identifying key concepts by reading the notes and the main concepts were put into categories.

Secondly, a rank of the order of the factors developed for each interview question and then the key retention factors were justified with the literature of the research.

3.10 Ethical consideration

Ethical conduct can be defined as morale values, confidentiality and anonymity of an individual, group or an organization. Confidentiality and anonymity usually refer to the declaration that researcher give to the participants that their identity and contribution in a research will be kept confidential. Quinlan (2011), cited by Tiwari (2015). In this study the respondents were informed of the confidentiality of their responses and anonymity of their identity through the informed consent form which was approved by instructor/supervisor of the research. The informed consent form was given along with questionnaire to the participants in the beginning of the interview. After the sharing of the informed consent form the participants knew about the purpose of the research, and signing the form will officially authorize them to participate in the study and allow the researcher to use their responses in the research. The informed consent form furthermore they have been informed that what is required from them as respondent. All the ethical codes were followed while conducting the research. Also, the answers given by the participants were kept confidential during the process of analysis. The participants were also guaranteed that the data gathered is sincerely for the research purpose. The participants were agreed to participate in the interview and fill-out the informed consent forms and signed it. To ensure confidentiality, participants were allowed to withdraw from the study at any time they may want. Participants were also permitted no to answer the questions if they were not feeling

convenient. Participants' forms were labeled with a two-letter code unrelated to names of participants. The participants' names were never shared and the data were stored securely.

Chapter 4: Data Analysis & Findings

The purpose of the study was to explore, what are the key factors that influence employee retention in a construction company located in Kabul, Afghanistan.

The aim of the study was to give an insight and actual employees thoughts to the owners of construction companies to retain their key employees for the sustainability of their business.

To obtain accurate data about the research topic, participants described their real concerns about their employment status and their expectations from their employer, explained which motivational factors are more important for their decisions to retain or leave their current employer and the data was analyzed by the researcher using mix-method. The demographic section of the questionnaire was analyzed through quantitative method and the open-ended questions section was analyzed using the thematic content analysis.

4.1 Participants Demographics:

The participants' answers to the demographic questions will be presented by the researcher as follow:

4.1.1 Position level:

Four participants were at the managerial level, and the rest eight participants were employed at the officer level. (Table 1)

Table 1: Position level

Position Level	Frequency	Percentage
Managerial	4	33.3%
Officer	8	66.6%
Total	12	100%

4.1.2 Gender:

Twenty five percent (25%) of the total participants were females and seventy five percent (75%) were males. (Table 2)

Table 2: Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Female	3	25%
Male	9	75%
Total	12	100%

The finding reveals that most of the employees of the construction company were males and there were only three female employees, however the researcher tried best to consider gender balance during data collection.

The researcher observed that none of the female participant were employed in the managerial level. The author observed that including females all officer level employees were mostly considering the rewards, and career development opportunities, offered by the company but the managerial level employees were mostly considering work environment and supervisor support.

4.1.3 Education Degree:

Fifty-eight-point three percent (58.3%) of the total participants were having bachelor's degree, Thirty-three-point three percent (33.3%) were holding master's degree, only eight-point three percent (8.3%) were just graduated from high school and none of them had doctoral degree. (Table 3)

Table 3: Education Degree

Degree	Frequency	Percentage
High School	1	8.3%
Bachelor	7	58.3%
Master	4	33.3%
Doctorate	0	0%
Total	12	100%

The finding revealed that there was no relation between education degree and employee retention factors, thus the author found that the education degree doesn't have any significant impact on the employee retention.

4.1.3 Education Field:

Forty-one-point six percent (41.6%) of the total participants were graduated from business administration field, sixteen-point six percent (16.6%) from engineering and sixteen point six percent (16.6%) from law and political sciences field, eight point three percent (8.3%) from Information Technology and the remaining eight point three percent (8.3%) had only graduated from school with no specific education field. (Table 4)

Table 4: Education Field

Education Field	Frequency	Percentage
Accounting & Finance	1	8.3%
Business Administration	5	41.6%
Economics	0	0%
Engineering	2	16.6%

Information Technology	1	8.3%
Law & Political sciences	2	16.6%
None (High school)	1	8.3%
Total	12	100%

The finding reveals that most of the employees were graduated from business administration field and also most of them are having bachelor degree, it means that people with business administration degrees are widely accepted in construction companies even more than engineers in the offices, it may be differed in the construction sites.

4.1.4 Construction sector experience:

Fifty-eight-point three percent (58.3%) of the total participants had six to ten (6-10) years’ experience in construction sector, sixteen point six percent (16.6%) had ten plus (10+) years, sixteen point six percent (16.6%) had four to ten (4-10) years, and only eight point three percent (8.3%) had experience in construction sector. (Table 5)

Table 5: Construction sector experience

Years of experience	Construction sector experience	Percentage
1 to 3 years	1	8.3%
4 to 6 years	2	16.6%
6 to 10 years	7	58.3%
Over 10 years	2	16.6%
Total	12	100%

4.1.5 Experience in current company:

Eighty three-point three percent (83.3%) of the total participants had over five years' experience in current company, eight point three percent (8.3%) had three to five years' experience, eight point three percent (8.3%) had one to three years of experience and none of the participants had less than one year experience in the current company. (Table 6)

Table 6: Experience in current company

Years of experience	Construction sector experience	Percentage
0 to 1 years	0	0%
1 to 3 years	1	8.3%
3 to 5 years	1	8.3%
Over 5 years	10	83.3%
Total	12	100%

The finding reveals that most of the employees being employed by the current company, didn't worked in the construction sector before, and also most of the employees haven't left their jobs over the five years of time.

4.1.6 Age group:

Forty-one point six percent (41.6%) of the total participants aged between twenty to thirty (20-30), Thirty-three point three percent (33.3%) aged between thirty one to forty (31-40), twenty five percent (25%) aged between (41-50) and none of the participants was aged above fifty (50) years of age. (Table 7)

Age group	Frequency	Percentage
20 to 30 years	5	41.6%

31 to 40 years	4	33.3%
41 to 50 years	3	25%
Over 50 years	0	0%
Total	12	100%

The finding reveals that the age group from 20 to 30 were mostly considering career development opportunities as the main retention factor, while the age group from 31 to 40 were considering work environment as the main reason of leaving the company and the age group from 41 to 50 were concerned more about supervisor support. Only one participant in the age group of 41 to 50 responded that he will leave the company if his rewards are decreased.

4.2 Open-ended question:

Totally six questions were presented by the researcher to the interviewee in this section.

4.2.1 First question:

What are three main reasons to work in the construction industry?

This question was general question asked from the participants and the answers were different as the most frequent answer was Learning/Experience/facing new challenges, the second frequent answer was, high salary/money, the third frequent answer was finding future opportunities and education related job, fourth answer was building the society and fifth was work satisfaction and least frequent answer was the only opportunity. (Table 7)

Table 7: Main reasons to work in the construction industry

Answers	Frequency	Percentage
Experience/Learning/facing new challenges	10	27.7%

High salary/Money	8	22.2%
Finding future opportunities	5	13.8%
Education related job	5	13.8%
Building the society	4	11.1%
Work satisfaction	3	8.3%
The only opportunity	1	2.7%
Total (participants * three answers = 36)	36	100%

4.2.2 Second question:

How are you motivated in your present job?

Although the question was answered with different word but the seventy five percent (75%) of the participants answers were Flexible hours/Work environment, sixteen-point six percent (16.6%) believed that supervisor support was important and just eight-point three percent (8.3%) answered that higher salary was important. (Table 8)

Table 8: Applied motivation Factors

Answers	Frequency	Percentage
Flexible hours/Work environment	9	75%
Supervisor support	2	16.6%
High salary/Money	1	8.3%
Total	12	100%

The finding reveals that the participants main motivation factor was work environment followed by supervisor support and the last one was rewards.

4.2.3 Third question:

If you leave the job what will be one key factor prompting you to do so?

The answers for this question are the most important for the study outcome as this question is directly related to the research question, what are the key factors influencing employee retention in the construction company. The data for this question will also be presented in the following table. (table 9)

Table 9: Job leaving factors

Answers	Frequency	Percentage
Lack of career development opportunities	5	41.6%
Poor work environment	3	25%
Lack of Rewards	2	16.6%
Lack of Supervisor support	1	8.3%
Total	12	100%

The finding clearly reveals that the most significant retention factor from the employee's perspective is career development opportunities followed by work environment, rewards and supervisor support.

After combining the second and third question answers it could be found that employees were not motivated with the career development opportunities but they said that lack of career development opportunities is the most significant factor for them to leave the organization, still they didn't leave the organization. During the interview, the author observed that the employees who wanted to leave the organization for lack of future career development opportunities were

not able to find a job elsewhere due to the economic situation in the country and they were somehow compelled to have at least a job to feed their family.

4.2.4 Fourth question:

What kind of intrinsic or extrinsic rewards have you received in your current job and how frequently?

This question was asked to know which kind of the rewards are the participant receive and how frequently, the data gathered from this question can be cross checked with previous question because the answers of the previous questions is co-related with this question. The data gathered is shown in the following table. (Table 10)

Table 10: Applied Rewards

Reward Type	Accommodation	Bonuses	Annual trips	Fuel	Health insurance
Percentage	100%	58.3%	41.6%	25%	16.6%
Employees	12	7	5	3	2

The finding reveals that none of the employees were offered intrinsic rewards. The company only offered extrinsic rewards as accommodation was accessible to almost all the employees, bonuses were offered to fifty-eight percent (58%) of the participants, Annual trips were also offered to forty-one point six percent (41.6%) participants, Fuel were offered to twenty five percent (25%) employees and health insurance was just offered to sixteen point six percent (16.6%) employees.

4.2.5 Fifth question:

What do you expect from your employer?

This question was asked to know what are the participant expectations from the employer, which will give insights about the expectations of the employees from their employer.

The data will be shown in the following table. (Table 11)

Table 11: Expectations from employer

Answers	Frequency	Percentage
Supervisor support	6	50%
Nothing	3	25%
Career development opportunities	2	16.6%
Rewards Increment	1	8.3%
Total	12	100%

The finding reveals that supervisor support was the most expected factor by the employees from the employer followed by career development opportunities and rewards increment.

4.2.6 Sixth question:

Is there anything you would like to share, or do you have any recommendations/suggestions, please?

This question was asked to ensure that nothing has been left through the course of questions but the answers from all the participants was no for this question.

Chapter 5: Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter starts with the review of data collection and analysis used to obtain findings from the data collected in the research following by limitation of the study and at the with the conclusion of the research.

5.1 Methodology and data collection review

The twelve participants who were employees of (XYZ) construction company located in Kabul, Afghanistan were the primary source of the data collection. The data collected from the participant through the semi structured questionnaire & face to face interviews within the (XYZ) construction company head office meeting room, were supported by the literature in the area of employee retention factors. The study data was collected in three weeks' time frame. Mix method were used to analyse the data, generated from the research.

The primary data consisted of the participants' perceptions and experiences related to the research main question, what are the key factors that influence employee retention in a construction company. The purpose of the interview questions was to identify which factors influence employees to stay in an organization.

In order to provoke the highest degree of possible accuracy, breadth, and depth of understanding regarding the topic of the study (despite of the socio-cultural constraints on data collection), the participants described actual retention and motivational factors that were used by the employer and answered which factors were more important to them. The researcher undertook one-on-one, face-to-face, semi structured interviews over three weeks in march and April 2021 to collect the data. During the interviews, the researcher listened for words and

phrases that identified how each retention factor contributed to the participants' retention in the company.

5.2 Analysis

This study aimed to find what were the key factors that influenced the employee retention in the construction company. Participant found the learning or getting experience, high rewards or salaries, and future opportunities to be the most important reason to work in the construction industry. The participants found work environment, supervisor support and high rewards or salary as the most important factor to be motivated in the job. The participants also found lack of career development opportunities, poor work environment, low rewards and lack of supervisor support as the main factors of companies left by the employees. The participants also discussed their expectations from the employer, in which the most important was the supervisor support following career development and rewards. Some of employees wanted to leave the company but they were compelled to do the job as they were not able to find another job which is an alert for the company because those employees are not engaged with the company they are just working with the until they find another job.

5.3 Conclusion and recommendations

The link between career development opportunities, work environment, rewards and supervisor support has been well established in the study. This research has assessed the aforementioned factors with multiple questions asked from participants and after analyzing all the data the researcher has come to the conclusion that the most important employee retention factor in (XYZ) construction company is career development opportunities following by work environment, rewards, and supervisor support.

The author recommends that to retain employees, construction companies which are operating in Afghanistan should consider career development opportunities, a good work environment, rewards, and supervisor support in developing their employment policies and strategies.

5.4 Limitation of the study

As all studies have some limitations, this research was also not different. Following were the limitation of this study:

- 1- Lack of academic literature availability on the research topic in Afghanistan and the literature were used from other countries and industries around the globe
- 2- The participants for this research were employees of only one construction company
- 3- The researcher's inability to use multiple data collection methods
- 4- Audio or video recordings for future reference were not done during the interviews due to company cultural values
- 5- Limited number of female participants were interviewed in the research due to low number of female employees in the company
- 6- Construction site employees and workers were not interviewed due to time and resources constraints

5.5 Recommendation for future research

To better understand what are the key factors that influence employee retention in Afghanistan companies, future researches may consider the following recommendations.

- 1- Include a large number of participants
- 2- Explore the topic in different industries

- 3- Explore the topic in different levels of the organizations to find if retention factors in other levels may differ
- 4- Replicate the study in Dari and Pashto, and include participants from different construction companies

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Appendixes

Appendix A: Consent form

Research title:	What are the key factors that influence employee retention in (XYZ) Construction Company?
Researcher & Institution:	Wais Patyalai MBA student in American University of Afghanistan
Interviewee:	

In order to assist the researcher with this thesis, I have agreed to be interviewed and to provide information and other materials to be used in connection with the thesis, including my personal experiences, remarks, and recollections as well as any photographs and documents that I may choose to give the researcher (the Interview Materials).

I confirm that I have reviewed the interview Materials, and [I hereby grant the researcher the following:

- permission to publish the Interview Materials for the life of the thesis – for academic purpose and to fulfil his degree requirements
- The right to use my interview as his data and other biographical data within the content of the thesis

I understand that this release does not restrict me from using the Interview Materials in any way I wish to.

I acknowledge and agree that I am not entitled to receive any form of payment from the researcher.

I warrant that the Interview Materials do not contain any unlawful statements, do not infringe any existing copyright or violate any proprietary rights, rights of privacy or publicity, or any other rights of any 3rd party.

Signed on behalf of the interviewee:

Name:		
Signature:		
Date:		

Appendix B: Questionnaire

As part of my MBA thesis at the American University of Afghanistan, I am conducting this survey to explore the factors that help employee retention in (XYZ) construction company. I would appreciate it if you complete the following questions. Any information obtained regarding this research will remain confidential.

Please make sure your responses are based on your best of knowledge as honestly and accurately as possible.

Section A: Demographic question

Please choose the correct answer by marking the answer box.

1- Please write your title/position: _____

2- Please specify your gender:

Female	
Male	

3- What is your education degree?

- High School Graduate	<input type="checkbox"/>
- Bachelor	<input type="checkbox"/>
- Masters	<input type="checkbox"/>
- Doctorate	<input type="checkbox"/>

4- What is your field of education?

- Accounting & Finance	<input type="checkbox"/>
- Business Administration	<input type="checkbox"/>

- Economics	<input type="checkbox"/>
- Engineering	<input type="checkbox"/>
- Information Technology	<input type="checkbox"/>
- Law & Political sciences	<input type="checkbox"/>
If other, please specify.....	

5- What are your years of experience in the construction sector?

- 1 to 3 years	<input type="checkbox"/>
- 4 to 6 years	<input type="checkbox"/>
- 6 to 10 years	<input type="checkbox"/>
- Over 10 years	<input type="checkbox"/>

6- How long have you been working in your current company?

- 0 to 1 years	<input type="checkbox"/>
- 1 to 3 years	<input type="checkbox"/>
- 3 to 5 years	<input type="checkbox"/>
- Over 5 years	<input type="checkbox"/>

7- Specify your age group:

- 20 to 30 years	<input type="checkbox"/>
- 31 to 40 years	<input type="checkbox"/>
- 41 to 50 years	<input type="checkbox"/>
- Over 50 years	<input type="checkbox"/>

Section B: Open-ended question

1- What are three main reasons to work in the construction industry?

2- How are you motivated in your present job?

3- If you leave the job what will be one key factor prompting you to do so?

4- What kind of intrinsic or extrinsic rewards have you received in your current job and how frequently?

5- What do you expect from your employer?

6- Is there anything you would like to share, or do you have any recommendations/suggestions, please?

Thank You